

Reviving Democracy Through Project-Based Learning— Grounded in Values, Equality, and Mutual Understanding

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Abstract.

In volatile times rethinking democracy includes reflecting respective approaches to education. In this contribution we investigate the potential of Project-based Learning (PjBL) for promoting the concept of democracy and those processes that (under)support democracy. We focus on role understanding and the dynamic of control between learners and teachers in PjBL. When the individual role perception of the participants can clarify their commitment or participation in favour of democracy-building learning effects, in the long run an egalitarian collective learning and living practice can be achieved. We detail how the individual and collective appreciation of role understanding within PjBL can create awareness and understanding of change processes. In PjBL, change agents may be encouraged to take responsibility on democratic processes and the design of collective behaviour. The lever towards viable democratic processes is the increased self-efficacy of teachers and students through PjBL, which is reflected in their engagement. However, special attention needs to be paid to teachers with regard to their attitude.

1 Introduction

It was John Dewey who intended to apply the ideas implied in a democratic society to educational problems, in particular methods of public education. His investigation sets theories of knowing in relation to early moral development and social conditions (Dewey, 1916). Thereby, Dewey set focus on the active acquisition of vital knowledge, skills, and habits through the learners' interaction in their social and natural environment. Accordingly, a project-based approach in education should embody democratic values and experiences as a form of coexistence.

Today, having many democratic structures observably under considerable pressure, we need to question whether Project-based Learning (PjBL) could be used in public education to revive and improve them. Although involving learners as active participants and giving them responsibility for their own projects can contribute to strengthening their democratic skills, it requires further design and facilitation effort to offer effective ways to experience, reflect on, and actively shape democratic culture in education (cf. <https://leap2020.home.blog/>).

Looking at democracy beyond its institutionalization, it thrives within everyday life practice, dialogue, the ability to compromise, and the willingness to take responsibility for the community. Consequently, crises or erosions of democratic cultures manifest not only in a loss of trust in institutions, but also in a growing susceptibility to (populist) simplifications (Samuelsson, 2016). Linking education with democracy therefore can refer to different approaches (Samuelsson, 2019):

- The educational system is consistent with democratic values, e.g., equal access to education;
- classroom practice engages learners in expressing their opinions and gives them (partially) control of their learning process, e.g., in school education;
- learners build capacity in terms of specific democratic skills, like knowing how to lead a discourse, and in this way are prepared for future democratic participation.

The latter is a non-trivial endeavor. For instance, it becomes more difficult for many (young) people to distinguish between objective criticism and personal attacks when they are primarily accustomed to polarized online discourse (Nishiyama et al., 2023). In addition, increasing social media penetration exacerbates existing tensions: polarization, disinformation, and echo chambers undermine the shared knowledge and experience upon which democratic understanding is built. Where complex social issues are addressed in simplistic friend-enemy dichotomies, the space for nuanced argumentation and for tolerating ambivalence shrinks (Cole, 2013).

Didactic analyses from political education indicate that without targeted learning opportunities for reflecting on media, power, and interests, young people are more susceptible to authoritarian or anti-democratic interpretations (Meyer et al., 2020). This complex situation — institutional erosion, media polarization, and societal fragmentation — sheds light on the fact that democracy cannot be taken for granted, but rather appears as a fragile project that requires learning and nurturing. Education thus becomes a crucial arena where democratic attitudes are either strengthened or weakened (Klemm, 2008; Samuelsson, 2016).

When democracy is considered as a way of learning and living, it needs to be instantiated in communication styles, conflict resolution, and shared responsibility. In educational institutions democracy needs to be experienced rather than being taught (Meyer et al., 2020; Nigar et al., 2024). These experiences need to include active participation in decisions, commonly owned liability for projects, and transparent negotiation processes (Klemm, 2008). When learners learn that their voice counts, and how they can argue and compromise, they practice on a small scale the very skills that a pluralistic society needs on a larger scale. However, such learning processes require a substantial shift from teacher-centered instruction towards giving space for responsibility, scope for decision-making, and room for experiencing consequences of one's own actions (Cole, 2013; Nishiyama et al., 2023).

Cole (2013) studied deliberative classroom projects and could demonstrate how participation in real-world negotiation processes significantly increases political interest and the willingness to participate in civic life later on. These findings correlate to results from applying PjBL when learners work on a meaningful question over an extended period, and the result of which becomes visible in a product, a presentation, or a concrete intervention. A key aspect is that knowledge is not only acquired but also applied to authentic problems, interconnected, and further developed collaboratively (Artama et al., 2023; Rehmann et al., 2024). Their empirical studies show accordingly that PjBL promotes 21st-century key skills such as critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, and citizenship skills, especially when addressing real-world societal problems. In project-oriented settings, learners take responsibility for planning, implementing, and reflecting on their work, and teachers act more as coaches or facilitators. They provide resources, asking questions, and supporting reflection, rather than being the dominant source of knowledge.

Given the described potential of PjBL, we detail its nature in the context of conveying and training democratic behavior in educational institutions. The contribution is structured as follows: Section 2

reviews major characteristics of PjBL. Section 3 depicts the potential to promote democratic structures in PjBL. Section 4 reviews existing findings. Section 6 structures and discusses the findings. Section 6 concludes the work and provides an outlook on future research.

2 Project-based Learning

The concept of project-based learning (PjBL) (cf. Blumenfeld, 1991; Bell, 2010), with its focus on learners' goals and self-directed action, has been a constructivist and (demonstrably still) forward-looking approach for over 30 years (Glavenu, 2022; Amelia & Santoso, 2020; Musa et al., 2011; Ravitz, 2010). PjBL also focuses on students and their pre-existing knowledge and implicit, intrinsic interest in research and knowledge (Blumenfeld, 1991; González-Pérez & Ramírez-Montoya, 2022). Accordingly, in this teaching method, teachers are seen as facilitators who focus on providing concrete needs-based support for the projects undertaken by the learners (Brailas et al., 2017; Lee et al. 2014; Mergendoller et al., 2006). Other essential elements of PjBL are the use of cognitive and technical tools for project processing (Krajcik & Blumenfeld, 2006), the requirement to develop solutions in an authentic context (and also to publish the corresponding results there for use), collaboration (Ayas & Zeniuk, 2001), as well as feedback (cf. Thurlings et al. 2013) and reflection as fixed components of the teaching concept (Krajcik & Blumenfeld, 2006).

Despite the already intensive global deployment of PjBL from primary and secondary schools up to universities (Indrawan & Jalinus, 2019), and the corresponding scientific research about the PjBL method over a long period of time (cf. Kokotsaki et al., 2016), it is still only implemented unsystematically and not standardised in institutions of higher education (cf. Naseer et al., 2025; Guo et al., 2020; Condliffe, 2017; Bradley-Levine et al., 2010).

In the context of a larger research project of the authors (see also Baum & Stary, 2023), the question was accordingly posed as to how this concept, which has been showing intensive appeal and testing worldwide for decades and has also already led to a conceptual framework (Larmer et al., 2015), can fundamentally be further developed by means of teachers' learning, based on their current state of knowledge and understanding of their role, at universities in increasingly virtual learning environments (Baum & Stary, 2022). The focus of the study was set on a potential transformation of organisational settings through behavioural changes, becoming visible in specific value-creating activities of teachers.

3 The Potential for Promoting Democracy in PjBL

Due to its inherent role shift between learners and teachers, PjBL is particularly suitable to illuminate the relevance of the participants' individual role perception for their engagement and active participation for the benefit of learning effects. Thus, it has the potential to contribute to democratisation based on self-responsible educational work in the sense of an egalitarian learning and living practice (Byram et al., 2023). Similar to democratic processes (cf. Miller & Davis, 2021), one's own understanding of the very own role is to be seen as a prerequisite for participation in (educational) processes. This paper will therefore bring to light the aspect of democratisation through and in educational work while deploying PjBL. As a result of this investigation, an understanding can be expected about which principles of PjBL are to be considered more closely with regard to equal or externally controlled behaviour.

Through the specific interweaving of role- and behaviour-oriented, organisational and technical issue, e.g., online teaching, digital learning environments, with reference to the perception of value exchange relationships, a further task area of the education system inevitably comes into focus, namely the maintenance and further development of the basic democratic values of our society, as was very aptly formulated almost 90 years ago in reference to educational institutions: *"School is,*

par excellence, the institution to which a democratic society is entitled to look for clarification of the meaning of democracy." (Bode, 1937, p. 95, in: Bullough, 2023, p. 10).

Another parallelism between democratic processes and educational processes can be found in the assumption that changes in behaviour, which often become visible in self-organised activities, can be traced back to (collective) cognitive processes on the one hand and to (jointly) developed values on the other. Last but not least, the given environment and the associated activity potentials of the participants also influence transformation processes of education towards promoting democracy. Induced by this context, we therefore need to ask to what extent the concept of PjBL is suitable both for the further development of educational work and for the promotion of democratic processes.

The article by Gergen (2023), *The Social Sciences as Future Forming*, which fundamentally refers to Glavenu with the statement that the currently necessary shaping of the future invites us to take a closer look at the prevailing educational and scientific formats. In this context, he explicitly ascribes a pioneering role to PjBL as a pedagogical practice that promotes exploration and innovation (Glavenu, 2022; in: Gergen, 2023). In his own words, Gergen describes this mindset as follows:

"The traditional orientation to scientific research makes a distinction between establishing knowledge and the application of this knowledge - ...Yet, if the sciences are concerned with building new futures, a shift in emphasis is needed: A premium may be placed on the actual creation of new configurations of cultural life. In Glavenu's (2022) terms, an ethics of possibility is imperative. In fact, one may derive an ethical orientation from the preceding emphasis on theories of co-constitution and co-creation." (Gergen, 2023, p. 4)

Following these explanations, it seems desirable to create a scientifically sound basis for transformative and future-oriented processes of the currently existing education system to strengthen democratic values. The aim of this critical analysis is therefore to establish an understanding of the importance of developing concrete democratic competences in the field of education and to relate the specific teaching concept of project-based learning (PjBL) to this. Accordingly, the research question for this research is derived from the above considerations:

To what extent do democratic forms of behaviour already examined in the context of PjBL show references to the pedagogical PjBL principles?

This, according to Bullough (2023), puts on a concrete lens through which the work of teaching and teacher education can be re-visioned, and turns the already existing view on learners as done in Brailas et al. (2017): *"Therefore, before answering the critical question, Why a group-based pedagogy?, we should answer the even more fundamental question, What is the finishing point we are looking for? What are those things that young people need to know, understand, and be able to do? What are the specific skills that are required by individuals to be functional and competent members of a modern society?"* (Brailas et al., 2017, p. 5).

In order to establish the current understanding of the roles of teachers and learners in the context of PjBL, while at the same time taking into account their possible activities and behaviour in order to compare them with the elements that constitute democracy, a scientific literature search was conducted. This is explained in section 3. The results were first pre-structured to facilitate further processing and essential assumptions/ starting points of PjBL on democratisation were summarised in tabular form. This is followed by a detailed description of the studies conducted to answer the research question. Based on this data, Section 4 answers the research question by bundling PjBL's main contributions to democratisation in educational work. Section 5 summarises the results in terms of a conclusion on democratisation with an outlook on further research and development activities.

4 Existing Work

In the following the procedure followed and search vocabulary used are detailed. Then, the results are given and structured for further analysis.

4.1 Literature search vocabulary and procedure

With regard to the literature search and its documentation, the "reasoned approach" of Van Wee & Banister (2023) was chosen for the reporting of literature reviews (see Figure 1). This approach is described below.

Table 2. The reasoned approach for reporting the methodology of a literature review paper.

Elements	Reasoned approach	Example
Databases	List the database(s) used for the search of papers Explain your choice	SCOPUS and Google Scholar We first searched documents in SCOPUS. Because the topic of this LRP, Artificial Intelligence, is rapidly evolving and academic publications might miss recent trends, we additionally searched for papers published in the past 24 months via Google Scholar.
Keywords and search string(s)	List the keywords and search string(s) Explicitly discuss the motivation. For example, discuss synonyms, different terms in different research areas that have about the same meaning.	(transport*) AND (health OR exercise) Because not all relevant papers use the term 'accessibility' we also searched for literature using related terms, i.e. 'connectivity' 'access' and 'proximity'.
Snowballing	State if you applied forward and/or backward snowballing Explain your choice	We applied backward snowballing departing from the references listed in Table [table number]. Because the first paper in this area were published less than 6 months before the date of searching, we only applied backward snowballing.
Selection of documents	State the principles on which you selected documents Include a table showing, or figure visualising how many papers were added/removed after each selection step	We selected papers based on titles, keywords and abstracts. See Le et al. (2022) (Figure 1) and Table 1
Results: documents found	Report the documents selected	A table reporting author(s), year of publication, topic, geographical scope, method(s) used
Additional selection criteria (if applicable)	Make explicit. For example, language, time frame, geographical scope Explain your motivation	We include English language documents only, published since 1990 related to the topic in OECD countries We only included documents published since 1990 because the methodologies used before that data are outdated – this would need to be supported by a key reference

Figure 1: Reasoning procedure in the literature review (Van Wee & Banister, 2023)

The decisive factor for the literature search was the recently published article by Bullough (2023) in: *Rethinking Dispositions in Teaching and Teacher Education: Virtue and the Manners of Democracy as a Way of Life*, which - although it does not directly discuss the concept of PjBL - 'rethinks' an essential element of project-based learning, namely the focus on the teachers' understanding of their role. Other core themes of this paper, which can only be identified indirectly through search vocabulary, were the focus on values as motivation in educational work, as well as the eye level to be established between learners and teachers. Accordingly, all three aspects were always taken into account when the author reviewed the documents and ultimately led to the selection presented below. A backward

or forward search in the sense of the snowball procedure (Badampudi et al., 2015; Jalali & Wohlin, 2012) was also not used due to the lack of a direct reference to the concept of the PjBL on the one hand and the novelty of Bullough's publication on the other. Therefore, the databases EbscoHost ([Datenbanken | EBSCO](#), n.d.), Emerald Insight (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/>, n.d.), ERIC ([ERIC - Education Resources Information Center](#), n.d.), SAGE Journals ([SAGE Journals: Your gateway to world-class journal research \(sagepub.com\)](#), n.d.), Scopus ([Why choose Scopus - Scopus benefits | Elsevier solutions](#), n.d.) or ScienceDirect ([About ScienceDirect | Premier platform for discovering peer-reviewed scientific, technical and medical information | Elsevier](#), n.d.), Taylor & Francis Online ([Taylor & Francis Online: Peer-reviewed Journals \(tandfonline.com\)](#), n.d.), Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>, n.d.), listed here in alphabetical order, have been searched for further relevant literature, as these are all peer-reviewed literature in the field of social sciences, economics or education, and thus promise to cover the topics of organisational development and democracy.

The descriptors that were specifically used were

„project based learning“ OR „PjBL“ OR „PBL“ „PBL education“ OR „project-based education“

in conjunction with AND

„democracy“ OR „equitable participation“ OR „egalitarian“ OR "democratic empowerment".

On the one hand, the search terms had to explicitly focus on the concept of project-based learning, and on the other hand, they had to establish a connection to the subject area of democracy education. The texts found also had to be accessible in English for reasons of linguistic processability and attention to the Western political education and economic area.

The literature search was also limited to the years 2000 to the present in order to obtain texts that show the current understanding and status of education and democracy development, on the one hand, and not to omit any fundamental research in this area, on the other. With regard to the journal rankings, no guidelines were set in order to also take into account academic 'side currents' of this topic, which have received less attention so far.

The corresponding database search yielded a total of 219 documents, which were then checked on the basis of the title and the contents of the abstracts for the above-mentioned three criteria: understanding of the role of teachers, focus on values in educational work, and eye level between teachers and learners. This analytical - not semantic - review of the publications found showed that some contributions on democracy already contain concrete proposals for implementation in educational work. Therefore, the reception of the results based on the abstracts of the publications was finally focussed on contents that contain guidelines that can be implemented in practice and establish transfer references between the concept of project-based learning and democratic forms of behaviour.

With the help of this procedure, seven publications could be selected for further analysis, which contribute complementary content over the course of the last 23 years on the specific connection between the democratic school of thought and PjBL, as well as trend-setting suggestions for its promotion. In the following, the corresponding reception is presented chronologically, and used in the next step along the research questions to answer them.

4.2 Results of the literature search

In the literature since 2000 on the teaching concept of PjBL on the one hand and the development of democratic behaviour and tendencies on the other, there has been a continuous development towards a multi-perspective treatment of the topic, mainly in the last eight years.

While Von Kotze and Cooper in their publication “Exploring the transformative potential of project-based learning in university adult education” already in 2000 fundamentally focused on the potential of PjBL to promote socially transformative types of learning based on international educational examples and thus created the basis for a corresponding understanding, 15 years later a concrete implementation attempt of a pedagogy based on PjBL, which focuses on strategies and principles for the development of tolerant behaviour, was also ventured by Voronchenko et al. (2015) in a multicultural context. A year later, Mosier et al. (2016) linked a specific known success factor of the PjBL approach, namely building community partnerships, to an innovative technology and democracy-promoting school model (the so-called New Tech Model) and investigated participants' perceptions of it.

Harmer and Stokes (2016), in turn, investigated in their study the actual degree of self-determination desired by students in the context of PjBL projects in order to draw conclusions about possible democratisation potentials of this concept. Finally, in 2021, Budiarti and colleagues examined the challenges and opportunities in the transfer of global PjBL practices by teachers into the classroom with regard to the Education for Global Citizenship movement (cf. González-Salamanca et al., 2020; Shultz, 2007) and the necessary acquisition of the so-called 4Cs (Creativity, Communication Skills, Collaboration, Critical Thinking; cf. also Ananiadou & Claro, 2009).

Finally, two seminal articles in this regard can be found in Dobson and Dobson's research, which proclaims a meaningful development of students' opinions of empowerment (Dobson & Dobson, 2021), and Bullough (2023), who seeks to challenge the status claims that teachers are supposed to have on learners in educational institutions by proposing an ethical and moral framework around teachers' attitudes.

The following table provides an overview of the articles mentioned and examined, divided according to the aspects conveyed in the abstract with regard to the categories of author, year of publication, thematic focus of the journal, type of publication, aim of the study, procedure of the study, results of the study, world view related to democratic values, and view of the educational mission of institutions. In order to provide insight into the original sources, all table entries have been left in the original language of the respective publication (English). For the sake of clarity, excerpts relevant to the research question are shown in italics or bold if they refer to democratic approaches.

Author(s)	Von Kotze & Cooper	Voronchenko, et al.	Mosier, et al.	Harmer & Stokes	Budiarti, et al.	Dobson & Dobson	Bullough
Year	2000	2015	2016	2016	2021	2021	2023
Sort of Journal	Studies in the Education of Adults	Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences	International Journal of Educational Reform	Journal of Geography in Higher Education	Journal of International Social Studies	Teacher Development	Journal of Teacher Education
Sort of study	Discussion paper	Experience paper	Survey study	Quantitative study	Survey study	Experience paper	Theoretical paper

Objective	Define and differentiate the potential of PBL to facilitate socially transformative kinds of learning	Implement a pedagogy of tolerance strategies & principles within PBL	Discover relationship of the PBL instructional approach to specific indicators of success of the New Tech Model with focus on a democratic school culture	Describe the potential of PjBL to foster democratization within the GEES disciplines	Give an overview of its challenges and opportunities as guide for educators to transfer Global PBL activities to classroom activities	Develop 'meaningful' student voice	Challenge status claims by ethic and moral framework for teachers
Means/ Approach	<p>Allowing students to construct new knowledge (action oriented & socially relevant)</p> <p>Emphasis on collective learning promoting an inclusive approach to knowledge production & dissemination; strengthening critical reflectivity & creativity</p>	<p><i>Role of a teacher shifted from expert to designer of reflective and collaborative projects</i></p> <p>Providing cooperative learning environments aimed to increase all possible contacts among culturally diverse students</p>	<p>Quest how high school students perceive the implementation success of a school reform organized around PBL, democratic school culture, and technology integration</p>	<p>Scrutinize student attitudes (to autonomy) in interdisciplinary PBL</p>	<p>Rendering teachers and students different views of their level of attainment of the skills of the 4C's</p>	<p>Evaluating project-based Character lessons taught by teachers and students (value-based instruction)</p>	<p>Regarding necessary teacher dispositions for enabling learning on the basis of democratic values</p>
Results	<p>The challenge facing university adult education in South Africa is how to use PBL not only to equip students with the means to survive in a 'risk society', but also to build their confidence and ability to challenge and re-negotiate the current terms of globalization.</p>	<p>Students who participated in the projects showed <i>higher tolerance to their classroom neighbours</i>.</p> <p>PjBL helps to master professional communication culture, overcoming communication barriers and becoming specialists with higher tolerance, ready to live and work in a multicultural society.</p>	<p>Positive relationships were found between PBL and indicators of success of a school reform called the New Tech School (NTS) model, which is organized around project-based learning (PBL), a democratic school culture, and technology integration.</p>	<p>Students favour prescription regarding research question and group membership within PBL with some degree of autonomy.</p>	<p><i>Learner-centered, constructivist, and reflective approaches</i> to teaching and learning did promote all 4Cs in one project.</p>	<p><i>Student empowerment is essential for student development.</i></p> <p>Challenging both consultative approaches to student voice and didactic values teaching, this project demonstrates that schools should create freer spaces for students to collaborate and develop their sense of agency.</p>	<p><i>Social vision / ethical and moral framework to guide and shape the work of teachers and teacher educators.</i></p>

Mindset according to democratic implications	Model of PBL origins in the social democratic concerns of linking student learning to real-life community problems.	Programs are developed in accordance with the recently adopted international and federal laws offering a perfect experimental platform to implement pedagogy of tolerance strategies through creative educational programs.	Intertwining of democratic and educational values.	Foster a more democratic approach to education , particularly through increasing students' autonomy over their learning.	Global citizenship, global competency, global civic engagement social responsibility & career competency.	Character lessons hold the potential to empower students and enable them to become more community-minded.	Democracy as a way of life vs. future employability concerns.
View on educational mandate	PBL can as easily be used to support the ideology of 'new vocationalism' as it can to support a more radical education agenda.	How can tolerant thinking among students be facilitated? Pedagogy of tolerance to grow up a new generation, prepared to communicate successfully in the globalized world.	Integrating a democratic and technological viewpoint within educational concepts.	Autonomy and collaboration as essential features of education.	4C's teaching strategies to enhance teacher planning.	Combination of <i>students-as teachers'</i> and PjBL approaches.	The educational process has no end beyond itself: it is continually reorganized, reconstructed & transformed.

Table 1: Literature reception (Own representation)

Von Kotze and Cooper (2000) consider PjBL as a vehicle from individual alienation to community agency when exploring the transformative potential of PjBL in academic occupational education. They refer in particular to PjBL's characteristic of not pre-determining learning paths in order to point to its potential to empower learning individuals to exploit new and unknown possibilities in terms of process and outcome. They also see a further link to democratic education in the association with service organisations and non-governmental institutions within these communities that is required in PjBL. This shifts the learning from the academic side to the outside, forcing students to apply their theoretical knowledge and research skills in the real world and enabling them to offer their services in areas where they can work after graduation. The individual selection of projects also supports early critical reflection on the relevance of topics and thus fosters a participatory view in education.

The performed as-is analysis indicated an instrumentalization of teachers and the vocational orientation of curricula taking precedence over the formation of critical faculties in institutions. The study introduced as counterpart of such neo-liberal understanding of education a learning practice situated in the centre of society for social development purposes, rather than as a purely academic exercise. While the latter approach, by abstracting and objectifying the problem, strengthens precisely the so-called professional elites in the sense of a scientific methodological competence reserved for them (without the claim to meet social challenges for their transformation), PjBL can serve as a means to support efforts to democratise and increase the social relevance of higher educational institutions. For example, community development with NGOs, which identify real problems as starting points and starting points for students. This allows students to engage in a social practice in which learning meant processing different levels of knowledge into practical knowledge in a balancing cooperative process. Such a setting can be seen as a collective alternative to self-directed learning and is not based on compensating for deficits, but supports learners to build on their

existing expertise and knowledge by addressing problems collectively in a variety of locations. In the process, new, activity-oriented and socially relevant knowledge is constructed, which nevertheless receives academic recognition.

According to Voronchenko et al. (2015), tolerance development through PjBL can help developing of human communities, since tolerance is one of the most important principles of interpersonal communication. It indicates political, legal, psychological and also ecological cultural maturity, as well as high social awareness and even intellectual and spiritual wealth. When designing a collaborative learning environment PjBL represents a system of working principles that necessarily establishes interdependence in all areas: it achieves mutual respect as well as self-acceptance with simultaneous tolerance towards other nations in international student groups.

To promote cooperation in mixed teams that share their different ideas and values, PjBL enabled testing future cooperation strategies and tolerance within a community. Thereby, the role of the 'teacher' changed from that of an 'expert' to that of a 'designer' of reflexive and collaborative projects. As such, designing individual plans for the students moved to the center of interest, in order to further develop their respective skills as well as social competences. They should include qualities to dissolve student individuality and identity, and to motivate them to engage with foreign cultures in a benevolent and open manner as a prerequisite for maintaining peace and avoiding intercultural conflicts.

Mosier et al. (2016) investigated democratic empowerment in the context of a PjBL integrating innovative school concept. They explored how students perceived the success of the implementation of a school reform model, a democratic school culture, and the integration of technology. The study evaluated the relationship of the PjBL-based teaching approach to specific indicators of success. As a result, a positive relationship was found, which makes the use of the novel New Technology School (NTS) concept together with PjBL recommendable for teachers. Specific to the NTS model is that students engage in democratic processes, giving them a voice in the classroom in the development of procedures as well as in decisions regarding lesson planning and teaching. Accordingly, students in NTS schools potentially have more nuanced opinions about their school experiences.

In the study, PjBL had its focus on fostering community-school collaborations, and on the development of an empowering culture of trust, respect and responsibility in which both students and teachers can be involved in school policy and curriculum development. The study found significant reinforcing links between PjBL and all of the above areas, 21st century learning, personal engagement, community cooperation and school culture. The authors conclude that the introduction of PjBL was generally strongly linked to a positive perception of the culture in the schools. Involving community partners in learning played a crucial role, encouraging teachers to look beyond the boundaries of the school for organisations with specific expertise. The curriculum was organised around these partnerships and partners were involved as much as possible in the teaching and learning process from planning to assessment. They served as experts who could share their expertise, give feedback on ideas and evaluate products developed in the process.

Self-determination and group composition as essential components of democratic processes and PjBL were studied by Harmer and Stokes (2016). They investigated students' perceptions of the relevance of autonomy with regard to topic choice and assignment to a project group in comparable projects in geography, earth and environmental sciences. In particular, they investigated the extent to which students wanted to be able to choose their research question and topic, the students' desire to be able to freely choose a project group, and the impact of students' experiences in this regard on the further autonomy of teaching in the subjects involved. The results indicate that students at this stage of their studies had ambivalent attitudes towards the degree of self-determination they preferred in conducting PjBL. The participants enjoyed working together across disciplines and found the contact with students from other programmes enriching as it allowed them

to discuss real-life problems. However, the involvement of academic supervisors was essential for participants who were at an early stage of their studies.

With regard to the democratisation aspect, the study raised the question of the extent to which PjBL as a democratisation tool in educational work serves the current primary teaching objective, namely the acquisition of vocational skills. The authors suggest that the principles and practice of democratisation in education should first be better clarified before they are given higher priority in the curricula. In this context, they argue, it is also necessary to match autonomy from a content perspective with social competences such as negotiation skills in a group. Intrinsic motivation to acquire competences as well as to organise the project work oneself was a decisive factor in both cases, as was the frequency and intensity of intervention on the part of the teachers (both for interdisciplinary work and for team building). Overall, interdisciplinary PjBL favoured the discussion on democratisation of educational work, as students also had to build up a social understanding of their roles within the project events.

In the study by Budiarti et al. (2021), the 4C key skills of the 21st century Communication, Collaboration, Critical Thinking, Creativity were examined with regard to implementation in schools. The starting point was overloaded and uncoordinated curricula and teacher-centred knowledge transfer. This led to a lack of engagement of the learners in the context of their knowledge acquisition. The remedy was to be Global project-based Learning (Global PBL), which has been proven to enable the authentic and sustainable embedding of the 4Cs. By means of extracurricular activities in the direction of global citizenship, a learner-centred approach to the 4Cs was developed together with teachers and students and implemented in projects in the sense of constructivist knowledge acquisition.

The understanding of the formation of democratic processes was thus framed by a theme, global citizenship. In this way it contributed to the learning goal and formed the context for the acquisition of 4C competences. Communication skills were developed, both in terms of expression and in terms of understanding information. The ability to work together concerned the individual approach as well as the group. At the individual level, this included taking responsibility, getting help from the team and respecting others. The group level included organising activities, negotiating to reach consensus and collective work processes. Critical thinking and problem solving started with creating questions and led through information gathering and evaluation to decision making processes regarding the solvability of a problem. Accompanying a solution path to evaluation was also part of the acquisition of this competence in a PjBL approach. Creativity and the ability to develop innovations were also based on finding information and ideas for solving problems or implementing novel concerns. The content of the project was planned outside the traditional curriculum and course operation under the students' own responsibility. Teachers were contacted and involved in the project activities as needed.

The data of the study, obtained through interviews, focus groups and protocols from field observations by the researcher, revealed that Global PBL can be used in a targeted way for the acquisition of the 4C competences, regardless of the chosen knowledge transfer strategy. From the teachers' point of view, the change of role towards facilitator was essential to support the students' own learning processes in PjBL. The authenticity of the tasks in Global PBL (selecting a recipe and sharing with international peers) as well as the extracurricular setting enabled the students to develop their knowledge both individually, and in the group, so that the learning process could be perceived as very positive. Overall, Global PBL created the conditions for democratic (learning and delivery) structures.

The space enabling collaboration and participation has been studied by Dobson & Dobson (2021) in the context of students' character education. They studied 'meaningful' voice development with knowledge-based curricula involving students from disadvantaged urban districts. The aim was

strengthening their awareness of democracy and familiarise them with the associated possibilities of articulation by means of value-based teaching. It opened space to work together and develop a sense of their own ability to act in a social environment. The data were collected through participatory action research and focus groups including role reversals between teachers and learners when achieving community-relevant results. The project reflection had an impact on the development of lessons and school plans.

From this study it can be concluded that in schools with a certain amount of free space, character building can be supported through personality development towards democratic awareness and a common good orientation of pupils, in particular through

- raising their own 'voice' in a meaningful way
- project-based action
- orientation of project-based action towards the common good
- value-led knowledge transfer

Bullough (2023) considers democracy as a way of life, and thus, as a social and moral framework which consequently applies to both knowledge transfer and learning processes. Challenging teachers' claims to hierarchy through a moral value system, the role of teachers must be addressed in terms of how socially responsible and morally acceptable teaching programmes can be developed. That distinguishes schools in democracies - they are predestined to develop the meaning of democracy. As an essential starting point for such a process, he sees the so-called status claims of teachers, which must be questioned and justified in every case. However, this requires both courage and tact, since evaluations (e.g., as part of accreditation measures) and the question of moral principles may be involved.

Both a social vision and a moral framework provide the framework for curriculum development and teacher action, as otherwise dispositional preferences could not be adequately justified. The consequence of this is that educational work is initially self-contained in this respect and is only subject to a continuous process of 'reorganisation, reconstruction and transformation' for itself.

So-called manners of democracy (expressions of democratic behaviour), instead of individual dispositions and virtues, simultaneously enable democracy building, according to Bullough (2023):

- *Hospitality* - as the teacher's approach to educational work, which in addition to friendliness also includes openness to discourse
- *Attuned Listening* - Listening to what students really need and grasping what the facilitator or teacher gives in terms of feedback to support the learning process.
- *Voice* - as a right of co-determination, such as for learners to decide for themselves, which project they want to do or which problem they find valuable and appropriate to solve.
- *Reflectivity* - individual and collective reflection, like the other forms of expression, is characterised by questioning evident information regarding the validity and justifiability of claims. It includes the search for information that will create clarity and thus lead out of a situation of uncertainty.
- *Evidential discernment* refers to the making and taking of meaningful decisions using a cognitive, justifiable, methodical approach that is appropriate to the circumstances of the technology and the objective.

The aforementioned expressions of democratic behaviour favour the development of knowledge and skills as well as virtues. The latter relate to the use of knowledge and skills in the same way as they are learned. They are also related to the individual objectives of learning processes. In this context, dialogue plays a decisive role, because it enables experiences to be gained, which are regarded as the primary source of knowledge. Due to their individual character, experiences set review routines in

motion, which favour the tension in learning processes in favour of absorbing new knowledge on the basis of existing knowledge.

In relation to the role of the teacher, this means that teachers become mediators who enable or facilitate individual cognitive processes. This should lead to a reassessment of the importance of dispositions in teacher education and training, and thus change the concerns that find their way into educational work. Orientation is provided by the five forms of expression mentioned above, which promote democratic practice and the assumption of action in favour of conversation, community orientation, and constructive further development even in the case of differing views.

5 How to Promote Democracy through PjBL

In this section, the democratisation potentials of the PjBL are first summarised on the basis of the previous presentation of research results and concrete interventions are discussed in order to finally answer the research question posed at the beginning.

5.1 Democratisation potentials of PjBL

From the present findings at the level of the framework conditions of institutionalised educational systems, several potentials of PjBLs for democracy-promoting behaviour in educational work can be uncovered, which are primarily derived from Von Kotze & Cooper (2000). They are summarised in the following.

- University adult education could be developed in terms of curricula that integrate more inclusion concepts and thus combine short-term goals in projects such as that of self-optimisation with long-term goals such as that of breaking down social hierarchies. In this way, students would not only come to university because they are aiming for a certain degree and title, but would have the opportunity to develop awareness for democratic values such as freedom, critical faculties and social responsibility in projects.
- Learning as a democracy-promoting process of interacting and acting in the world through PjBL processes (re)locates learning in the (original) community- and society-related context. This should entail a socially relevant appreciation of education, whereby the educated give something back to their community.
- On a collective level, PjBL processes can counteract a deficit-oriented teaching concept with the help of 'strengthening strengths'. At the same time, power dynamics within groups due to age and competence differences can be part of PjBL processes that require democratic patterns of action. Furthermore, the need for a community of practice, as established in PjBL, requires the building of a group identity with shared opinions and priorities. Finally, the goal of collective learning is to produce new knowledge that represents the negotiated interests of all.
- Traditional patterns of relationships between experts and non-experts can be broken within the framework of PjBL through the participants' own activities - democratic negotiation processes can take the place of the delegation of tasks. In this way, PjBL can be used for pre-vocational training as well as for supporting a 'more radical education agenda'.

Within the framework of democratic or democracy-promoting PjBL processes, the joint negotiation of meaning, the questioning of power relations and academic discourse should thus be given a higher priority than the knowledge that is acquired within the framework of these processes.

5.2 Design proposals for democracy-promoting PjBL

From the present summaries in chapter 3, behaviour conducive to democracy can also be derived at the operational level of educational work as well as the relationship level between the teachers/facilitators and learners. The following characteristics of PjBL are taken into account:

- PjBL transforms teacher-centred knowledge creation and transfer through learner-teacher collaboration
- Not only do learners choose the thematic content on a project basis, but they also form their respective project groups independently.
- The discussion about the project-related contents starts with the planning of the projects - the groups present the results of the planning processes to each other.
- The exchange takes place in regular meetings - work results are reported, learning success is discussed and the respective follow-up phase is planned.
- The results of the learning processes are evaluated by the participating organisations or those responsible for education, for whom a collective report is written. In addition, both content and process are considered in a collective evaluation process. Thus, both the participation in the group events and the quality of the results are included in the evaluation.
- Learning takes place on several levels: on the group level and on the individual level as a student or teacher.

In the following, these characteristics are bundled and presented in the context of democracy-promoting activities and behavioural traits.

Learning situated in the community promotes an understanding of democracy

PjBL starts from a social field in which learning takes place. The social context is therefore conducive to democracy, and not only in educational institutions. The KU Leuven model of PjBL, for example, originally distinguished itself from cognitive learning models in that the main locus of learning moved out of the academic world and into real organisations. There, from the point of view of this teaching concept, is not only the concrete production of value and knowledge, but above all with it the power to act. Learning is thus directly linked to participation in and shaping of public life. Students not only have to learn how to reach agreements among themselves, but also how to negotiate with the authorities in the respective organisations, analogous to the situation with their academic supervisors.

Collective learning through collaboration promotes engagement with democratic processes

Equally fundamental in relation to PjBL, according to Von Kotze & Cooper (2000), is the collective process of learning: success as well as failure is largely dependent on the ability of the project group to establish a group identity and a common way of working.

In their example, students basically work in a mixed group of six to eight participants from different years who support each other and jointly generate meanings within their learning process. Here, too, the parallel to democratic processes can be found in the fact that this competence constitutes an essential dimension of learning, which is also formally evaluated by all participants (by the group, by the members, and by the teachers): "Each group member is evaluated in relation to her contribution to the functioning of the group in its learning process, and in terms of the project task at hand. Thus, it is important for students to consider themselves as functioning parts of a whole, as members of a community, thus strengthening collective values." (Von Kotze & Cooper, 2000, p. 218). Derived from these considerations, the possibility of 'thinking through the body of the group' is suggested in PjBL: Through the interaction of the group participants and those with social practices in the organisations, they can, for example, experience strong emotional reactions together.

Collective learning in this sense always means 'effort, confrontation, interaction, collision, cooperation and adaptation' (Wenger, 1998, p. 46; in Von Kotze & Cooper, 2000), while 'teamwork' is defined by adherence to rules and norms. Both types of associations build on the strengths of their members, but unlike teams, collectives, according to Von Kotze and Cooper, offer their participants the freedom to try out different roles and experiment with different behaviours in a protected environment.

Criticality and creativity as a prerequisite for democratic experiences

Criticality requires dealing with contradictions and tensions as well as power structures. It is a prerequisite to start transformations processes. PjBL can initiate the process of questioning what seems natural and normal by exposing or at least challenging the invisible mechanisms of work and the forces that move them (Newmann, 1999; in: Von Kotze and Cooper, 2000). Accordingly, from the authors' point of view, it serves not only to prepare students to survive in a 'risk society', but also to test and renegotiate their self-confidence and ability to cope with the current conditions of globalisation.

Formation of tolerance as an individual and collective feature of democracy

Voronchenko et al. (2015) describe tolerance as both a social value and a personal attitude. PjBL courses that require a high degree of intercultural communication can facilitate the development of ethnic tolerance. As a result of a related study, participants who attended such projects showed a higher tolerance, which enabled them to overcome communication barriers in a multicultural society. The researchers conclude that PjBL not only produces professional competences, but also the culture of tolerance of a person who is able to change the world community in a positive way.

Empowering students through trust, respect and responsibility - cornerstones of democratic behaviour

Learners whose teachers used PjBL more intensively and frequently reported a more positive learning experience, more engagement and greater community involvement. They also believed they had developed 21st century skills by collaborating with others to solve problems through the completion of relevant projects. They had positive perceptions of community partnerships and believed they had made their own contribution to a participatory school culture. Overall, there was a correlation between students who were engaged and their positive learning experience as a whole. In addition, many students reported that they had been openly involved in shaping rules, curricular decisions and assessments on an equal footing. It became clear that this increased their sense of responsibility for their school experience. A sense of belonging, similar to that of a family, was mentioned (Mosier, et al., 2016).

Role and requirements for characteristics of teachers

If, as suggested by Mosier et al. (2016), the so-called PjBL Index is to be an effective measure for PjBL educational work and is to be used by managers or administrators in the future for teacher evaluation in schools that want to use PjBL as the main teaching method, the teachers' understanding of their role and their attitude towards PjBL will play a decisive role.

In addition to the basic understanding of the role in traditional educational work and in PjBL and the associated behavioural reflection in dealing with learners for the further development of educational work (Akert & Martin, 2012), the so-called manners of democracy represent forms of expression of democratic behaviour in all participants of the learning process, which promote democracy building (cf. Bullough, 2023), which are summarised again here:

- Educational work should be based on an inner commitment to the transfer of knowledge in the PjBL, whereby dialogue and discourse become central means of understanding and understanding-building.

- If this appreciation is accompanied by active listening, articulated learner needs can flow into support services and eventually into active learning guidance, so that inputs and feedback from teachers actually support learning processes.
- Guidance and leadership at eye level give the learners the right to have a say, which creates the freedom of decision-making and design in the PjBL, in order to have a sustainable effect in promoting democracy through its role model effect.
- Individual and collective reflection is not only conducive to dialogue and discourse, but also brings to light assumptions and attitudes that are essential in the context of democracy-building and ultimately democratic processes. Thus, the validity of information and the justifiability of statements are central – it enables democratic action in practice.
- Reflective action ultimately fosters informed decision-making processes and meaningful choices in and for the community. This enables collectives to become resilient and to act in an evidence-based and coordinated manner in complex situations or crises.

In order to develop these forms of behaviour, the training of teachers is of decisive importance. Personal disposition and attitudes towards the transmission of knowledge, understanding, excellence as well as socially relevant development processes in PjBL and democracy-building processes play an essential role alongside organisational embedding in educational institutions (cf. Grieve, 2010; Akert & Martin, 2012). They determine the individual and organisational scope for action, which needs to be rethought and ultimately shaped.

From the perspective of organisational agency, it is important to note that teacher empowerment in terms of design has a much stronger impact on their satisfaction when it is anchored in the respective organisational context, and not only at the level of supporting individuals. Consequently, educational leaders and institutionalised bodies should focus on different qualities of teacher empowerment. At the disposition regarding the components of satisfaction that can be promoted is especially self-efficacy (Bogler & Nir, 2010). This closes the circle to PjBL: If it is possible to implement PjBL as a co-creative, collaborative and co-educational process, structures relevant to democracy can be worked on by all stakeholders involved.

Some of these findings have been confirmed in recent studies. In an elementary school setting, PjBL affected positively and significantly the democratic practices of equality, engagement and justice (Daher et al., 2024). All of these results provide a well-defined starting point and input to professional development (programs). For instance Kavanagh et al. (2025) features outcomes of a practice-based professional development for middle and high school teachers to develop and enact a set of teaching practices for PjBL when developing democratic structures. Thereby, teaching practice is reconceptualized as a communal activity rather than an individual one. While this approach is based on Cultural Historical Activity Theory (CHAT), Brin et al. (2021) suggest to follow Dewey's 'pedagogical creed', that education is the fundamental method of social progress and reform. Defining the role of a teacher as a member of the community, learners are guided to share their insights as part of social consciousness. The applied principles are: learning appropriate roles, frequent opportunities for formative self-assessment, and social organizations that promote participation and results in a sense of agency. Once these principles become part of curricula, as shown by Clancey et al. (2024) in a case study, democracy-oriented PjBL education becomes sustainable in terms of expanding civic engagement or deepening democracy.

5.3 Answering the research question

Since PjBL is particularly suitable for working on an understanding of democracy and self-responsible participation in democratic processes due to the shift in roles between learners and teachers inherent in this concept, potentials could be identified both on an institutionalised/organisational as well as on an individual role level. These allow research questions on the further development of PjBL per se, but also to consider the principles of PjBL with regard to equal and/or leadership behaviour.

Whereas the former focuses on the understanding of roles in PjB learning processes, the latter focuses on the visible or invisible value-creating activities of teachers and learners in democracy-reflecting and democracy-building processes.

The research question posed at the beginning of this paper, i.e. to what extent democratic forms of behaviour already examined in the context of PjBL show references to the pedagogical PjBL principles, can therefore be answered as follows: Several principles of PjBL can be considered more strongly with regard to equal or/and leadership-guiding behaviour. These predominantly refer to the connection between the understanding of the role of teachers and the associated patterns of action within the framework of the further development of educational work and democratic processes. In educational work with PjBL, all interactions between teachers and learners can be regarded as democracy-building and -promoting, which

- have or establish a community connection, and
- focus on appreciative leadership (also in higher organisational instances).

Both create space for creative knowledge generation within the framework of collaborative and at the same time autonomous learning processes to envision a new approach to teaching and teacher education.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

“What has become evident is that there are at least two models of Pbl: one is the ‘ideal version’ in the ‘old’ social democratic framework, while the other is a more recent development adjusted to the demands and constraints of the neo-liberal environment.”

(Von Kotze & Cooper, 2000, p. 226)

From what has been said so far, it can be concluded that PjBL has fundamental potential for promoting an understanding of democracy and processes that (under)support democracy, especially if it is used in the sense of the above quotation from Von Kotze & Cooper in an ideal way. The reason for this lies in the processing of role understandings, whereby a change of position between learners and teachers takes place in PjBL processes. In this way, the individual role perception of the participants can clarify their commitment or participation in favour of democracy-building learning effects and, in the long run, establish an egalitarian collective learning and living practice. If the principles of PjBL are increasingly taken into account with regard to equal or/and leadership guiding behaviour towards democratic behaviour, several societal consequences can be assessed (cf. Von Kotze & Cooper, 2000):

- Even if the terms used by representatives of the 'new capitalism' and its counter-movements (Gee et al., 1996) coincide or are very similar, democracy-promoting behaviour will be able to spread. Thus, terms such as liberation, empowerment, trust, vision, collaboration, teams, self-directed learning, quality, etc. will be characterised by individual or collective appreciation.
- PjBL is suitable for initiating professional empowerment, as it enables people to experience a market-oriented reality while at the same time critically reflecting on the current economically oriented conditions in the project.
- In this tension, PjBL becomes a "change agency" (Fullan, 1993; in: Harada & Hughes-Hassell) that can be communicated by teachers and learners, i.e. creating awareness and understanding of change processes. In PjBL, change agents can be encouraged to act on their own responsibility in a collective that has to move in a social environment and can be invited to experience.

- The lever towards viable democratic processes is the increased self-efficacy of teachers and students through PjBL, which is reflected in their engagement. Special attention should be paid to teachers with regard to their attitude and their approach to mediation: "Teacher self-efficacy, defined as teachers' beliefs in their own capabilities to be effective teachers (...), has been found to be associated with a variety of teacher characteristics and behaviour (...)" (Choi, et al., 2019, p. 45).

It can be deduced from the last statements that learning processes in PjBL should be viewed from the perspective of the collective, whereby the group 'carries' learning processes that are primarily characterised by mutual perception of content: "students are confronted by different interpretations from their peers, and learning proceeds by comparing, contrasting and criticising these interpretations" (Jackson & Prosser, 1985, in: Brailas, et al., 2017, p. 6).

Facilitators in this setting have the task of helping to build a working culture. Their support manifests itself in the negotiation and consensus-building of accepted and practicable rules of conduct. This primarily social development process must be given time and space. It also requires methodological support. As part of the support for the creation of a project-specific working culture for mastering the PjBL process, facilitators also enter into learning processes that they can use for the development of the group but also for their personal development (Brailas, et al., 2017). If teachers take advantage of this opportunity, this form of co-evolution means socially relevant development of democracy, as collective changes can be justified and accepted on the basis of the development of individual role understandings. The situation is similar for those responsible for education in organisational leadership functions such as school headmasters (Arkert & Martin, 2012).

Consequently, nothing stands in the way of a democratically developing global citizenship as conceived by Reimers et al. (2016). If educational work aims to promote a democratic sense of responsibility and to strengthen the imagination and creativity of learners through PjBL and the associated systematic, team-based approaches to complex problems, then it is important to promote a corresponding anchoring in curricula and study programmes, as presented by Fadel et al. (2015). This should aim at character building as well as teaching the necessary competences for personal development and participation in the development of a collective in times of increasing networking.

The crucial consequence of this focus is that while primarily the learners are targeted by democracy-promoting PjBL – "Young people need to know, understand, and be able to do things that they wouldn't if left to their own devices" (Robinson & Aronica, 2015, p. xii), teachers can be also targeted. They can be addressed by this form of capacity building. Consequently, a step-by-step development process can be entered into together in the sense of a planned process of imperceptibly growing into a new culture of learning, a so-called "planned enculturation" (Osberg, 2005, p. 81f).

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